

Housing associations as the new Great Estates: Uncovering corporate landownership in London

Susannah Cramer-Greenbaum,^{*1} Malcolm Morgan²

¹Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, University College London, ²Institute for Transport Studies, University of Leeds

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Summary

Landownership matters. As a mostly finite and highly valued resource, landownership often aligns with concentrations of wealth, constellations of power, and significant social stratification, while capably concealing illicit financial activity and tax avoidance. London is no exception; rather, London is an exceptional exemplar of land-based wealth and social stratification. UK landownership is a closely guarded secret, held by the often-inadequate data infrastructure of His Majesty's Land Registry. This project parses messy and only partially available landownership data to make accessible new datasets showcasing the distributions of corporate, private, and public landownership in London, along with London's largest landowners.

KEYWORDS: landownership, land registry, corporate-owned land, open data, London

1. Introduction

In her 1986 book *Who Owns London?* Shirley Green writes: “The property world is paranoically secretive about its activities, and rather as in the world of espionage, works on a furtive ‘need-to-know’ basis. This paranoia extends from private individuals to major financial institutions like the pension funds and insurance companies, who for the most part, although they are investing the public’s money, keep the public in as much ignorance as possible.” In the intervening 40 years not much has changed. Green implicitly claims the public have a right to know how their money is invested and spent through disclosing land ownership, and disclosing landownership remains a challenging task.

Long cloaked in secrecy, UK landownership has recently, by incremental degrees, begun to become slightly more transparent, in part thanks to activist pressure (Cahill, 2001; Green, 1986; Powell-Smith, 2025; Private Eye, 2016; Shrubsole, 2019, 2025) and academic research on overseas corporation owned land (Bomare & Le Guern Herry, 2025; Bourne et al, 2023). There was no central register of landownership in the UK until 1862. Since 1862 the land registry has existed for voluntary registration, until 1925 when government-initiated areas of compulsory registration became allowed. In 1990 land registration became compulsory in England and Wales, but only at point of sale. Today 89% of land in England and Wales is registered. While a somewhat complete land registry now exists, the data is still behind a paywall. To access a single title costs £8.50 + VAT, plus a processing fee, and the data structure of the land registry files makes providing enough information to even locate a title for purchase challenging.

While most of the land registry data is still inaccessible, in 2016 the Land Registry started publicly

* s.cramer-greenbaum@ucl.ac.uk

releasing some data on corporations that own land in England and Wales (HM Land Registry, 2020a; 2020b). This dataset includes overseas corporations, UK for-profit corporations, not-for-profits and local authorities, excluding only those listings held by private individuals. As this paper discusses, the data, while public, is still quite opaque, presenting significant difficulties in extracting any useful data for further analysis. The current [2026] national government has signalled support for making more land registry data available in a more usable form (Shrubsole, 2025). Hopefully they will, as land data is critical for researchers in understanding economic and social foundations of cities and society.

In the meantime, this paper undertakes to unpack and attempt to make usable the data available. This paper uses the corporate-owned land dataset, querying 1) how much land in Greater London is owned by what kind of corporation, 2) how that land is distributed throughout Greater London, and 3) who the largest landowners in London are. By parsing this valuable but messy data, and making several cleaned and accessible London landownership datasets publicly available on the Open Science Framework, this project enhances collective knowledge about London landownership, shedding light on one of the fundamental drivers of wealth inequality and social stratification in the city.

2. Data and methods

This project combines data from four sources. The first is the Land Registry data on corporate owned land, including public corporations such as local authorities or the Greater London Authority (GLA). Land Registry releases information on corporate-owned land in England and Wales monthly, including the name of the proprietor, address at which the proprietor is incorporated, corporate classification of the proprietor, and address of the land. The project uses the land registry data released through November 2024. Except for the address field, and an often empty postcode field, the data is not linked to any spatial information other than the borough or county, and these fields are often missing also. The address field presents the greatest challenge; it is a free text field in which the property can be described in any number of ways, and often includes multiple land parcels within one listing. The aim of this project was to parse these listing into legible individual addresses, and geocode them to locate the properties spatially across London.

We aligned the geolocated addresses to the INSPIRE parcel dataset (HM Land Registry, 2020), a shapefile of all registered land parcels in England and Wales, made publicly available by the UK government. Each parcel is assigned a unique INSPIRE ID, and associated to the relevant borough or local authority, but contains no address information.

To check the accuracy of overlaying the address geocoding on INSPIRE parcels, we compared the results for public corporations with data scraped from the Mayor of London's Public Land map, which pulls its information directly from the land registry through channels unavailable to the public. We also purchased 484 landownership titles from the Land Registry for the largest non-publicly owned parcels in Greater London, to further corroborate the geocoded results.

Using R, we parsed the raw dataset (Morgan, 2025), following the logic described in **Figure 1**, coded the corporation types, and cleaned and standardized proprietor names. We geocoded and mapped the distribution of freehold land holdings in QGIS.

Figure 1 Parsing logic for complex address field listings

3. Findings

The results found by analysing the geocoded and corroborated data can be categorized in three groups:

3.1 Data challenges

The myriad challenges working with the land registry data go deeper than expected and include incompetencies within the land registry’s own internal data infrastructure. The publicly available land registry dataset includes no geospatial information, other than a messy free text address field. However, the land registry itself had trouble locating title information for 76 out of the 560 addresses requested for purchase, based on the address information the land registry itself provided. This presents some serious challenges in getting accurate data and raises some major questions on how accurate the land registry’s own data is.

3.2. Largest landowners

While the largest collective group of landowners in London is the borough councils, the second largest by far is housing associations, which together own at least 3.5% of the registered land in the city, and likely more give the underestimation tendency of the geocoding described below. Historically, the Great Estates were London’s landlords. Today housing associations own at least 14x as much land as the present-day estates. Amongst the largest individual landowners housing associations represented five out of the top twenty (**Table 1**). Other top-100 individual landowners include some likely suspects (Transport for London, London Underground Limited, and GLA Property and Land Limited), and golf clubs, the Scouts, Veolia, Prologis, and All Souls College Oxford. There are surprises – defunct London governments (Greater London Council and the London County Council) still have land registered to them, along with pre-1965 local authorities which no longer exist. 12.34% of the land in London is unregistered.

Table 1 Top largest Greater London landowners

Rank	Landowners	Cumulative % of registered land
1	Crown Estate	1.7%
2	Thames Water	2.5
3	London & Quadrant (housing association)	3.1
4	Heathrow Airport	3.7
5	Borough of Hillingdon	4.2
6	Clarion (housing association)	4.7
7	Peabody Trust (housing association)	5.2
8	Borough of Enfield	5.7
9	Borough of Barking and Dagenham	6.1
10	City of London	6.5
11	Secretary of State for Transport	6.9
12	Borough of Croydon	7.3
13	Notting Hill Genesis (housing association)	7.6
14	Borough of Barnet	7.9
15	Borough of Greenwich	8.1
16	Borough of Havering	8.4
17	Wimbledon & Putney Commons Conservators	8.7
18	Borough of Bexley	8.9
19	Southern Housing (housing association)	9.2
20	Borough of Bromley	9.5

3.3. Comparative spatial distribution of ownership types and open data

When partially assessed against the GLA public land maps, the parsed and geocoded addresses tended to underestimate corporate owned land areas and overestimated individual address counts. However, the geocoded data correlated well to the GLA data in comparative ranking for top landowners, and distributional spread aggregated at the middle statistical output areas (MSOA) and borough level. For this reason, we have made public the following datasets on Open Science Framework (OSF) at the following doi:

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9STJ3>:

- Shapefile and csv with areas for percentage of land owned by local authorities, non-profits, UK for-profit corporations, and overseas for-profit corporations, both by borough and MSOA, and including an underestimation error factor and 95% confidence interval (**Figure 2**).
- Shapefile and csv of 1000 largest London parcels with INSPIRE ID, owner information, and owner type, representing ~23% of registered land in London (**Figure 3**).
- Shapefile and csv with areas for percentage of land owned by housing associations, both by borough and MSOA, and including an underestimation error factor and 95% confidence interval.
- Shapefile and csv of GLA public land map with INSPIRE IDs and proprietor information.

Figure 2 London landownership

Figure 3 London large parcels

4. Conclusion

This study aims to parse and make accessible some of the excessively opaque and messy data that constitutes the land registry in England and Wales. Increasing access to this data, despite its limitations and challenges, increases transparency in landownership, long a closely guarded secret in the UK. And increasing landownership transparency offers opportunities for further research to reveal some of the underlying mechanisms of London’s extreme wealth disparities and spatial inequalities.

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References

- Bomare, Jeanne and Le Guern Herry, Ségal, Avoiding Transparency through Offshore Real Estate: Evidence from the United Kingdom (2025). *EU Tax Observatory Working Paper*. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5260099>
- Bourne, J., Ingianni, A., & McKenzie, R. (2023). What's in the laundromat? Mapping and characterising offshore-owned residential property in London. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 50(9), 2430-2451. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083231155483>
- Cahill, K. (2001). *Who owns Britain*. Canongate.
- Green, S. (1986). *Who owns London?*. Weidenfeld and Nicolson.
- HM Land Registry. (2020, 26 May). *UK companies that own property in England and Wales*. UK Government, HM Land Registry. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/hm-land-registry-uk-companies-that-own-property-in-england-and-wales>
- HM Land Registry. (2020, 26 May). *Overseas companies that own property in England and Wales*. UK Government, HM Land Registry. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/hm-land-registry-overseas-companies-that-own-property-in-england-and-wales>
- HM Land Registry. (2020, 3 July). *INSPIRE Index Polygons spatial data*. UK Government, HM Land Registry. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/inspire-index-polygons-spatial-data>
- Mayor of London. (2022). *Mayor of London public land map*. Mayor of London. <https://www.london.gov.uk/programmes-strategies/housing-and-land/land-and-development/public-land-map>
- Morgan, M. (2025). Carbon & Place: Data and tools to understand the spatial variation in carbon footprints. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083251401613>
- Powell-Smith, Anna (2025) *Anna Powell-Smith*, Available at: <https://anna.ps/> (Accessed 23 January 2026).
- Private Eye (2016) *Selling England (and Wales) by the pound*. Available at: <https://www.private-eye.co.uk/tax-havens> (Accessed: 23 January 2026).
- Shrubsole, Guy (2025). *Who Owns England?*. Available at: <https://whoownsengland.org/> (Accessed: 23 January 2026).
- Shrubsole, G. (2019). *Who owns England?: how we lost our green & pleasant land & how to take it back*. William Collins.

Biographies

Susannah Cramer-Greenbaum is a Research Fellow hosted at UCL's Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis

Malcolm Morgan is a Senior Research Fellow for Transport and Spatial Analysis at the Institute for Transport Studies, University of Leeds.